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Transversality for circularity and sufficiency in Grenoble

Follow-up report

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Grenoble

Executive summary

The project

This is a follow-up report from the activities of a team of early-career researchers, supported by mentors and project managers from the SSH CENTRE Knowledge Brokerage program, working in partnership with the City of Grenoble (FR). The goal of this partnership, which took place in 2023 and 2024, was to apply social science and humanities research to the topic of sufficiency and circularity of resources in Grenoble through methods inspired by the Knowledge Brokerage literature. After initial study of the context and research, and consultation between the partners, the research project focused on promoting transversality (communication and collaboration across institutional borders and administrative silos) between departments within the city in such a way as to help Grenoble's citizens change their behaviour towards greater sufficiency.

The research project had 3 main components: a survey sent to Grenoble employees, workshops with participants from the municipality and six other cities across Europe during a City Hub event in April 2024, and this report sharing the findings and giving recommendations.

Main findings

The survey, which focused on the topics of sufficiency and transversality, showed a segment of Grenoble's employees, mostly managers or senior managers, with a generally high level of knowledge and motivation related to sufficiency. For most respondents, these issues are already integrated into their daily work including (for some) their contact with citizens. However, many of these employees had little or no direct contact with Grenoble's population related to sufficiency. On transversality, all employees engaged regularly in collaboration and knowledge exchange with other departments, but most consider that internal knowledge sharing in the city (and with its inhabitants) could be improved. The survey collected a number of suggestions to improve internal and external communication.

The workshops brought together a range of perspectives from inside and outside of Grenoble. In the first of the two parallel sessions organised by the research team, municipal employees came together to discuss issues related to participatory democracy, the role of the city administration as an example for its citizens, and the impacts of values and norms (both within the city and its population) on sufficiency issues. In the second session, representatives from the 6 guest cities shared challenges, experiences, and best practices on implementing transversality and encouraging citizen behaviour change. Other smaller workshops throughout the two-day City Hub event surfaced important issues such as the human resources implications of sustainability transitions, challenges with encouraging diversity in participatory processes, and the decisive role of frontline employees in achieving city ambitions.

Recommendations

This report briefly summarises the numerous ideas, suggestions, best practices, and successful experiments shared by the participants in the City Hub event. In addition, it provides further details on three particularly pertinent avenues for development: empowering frontline employees, connecting the city's work with key actors in the community, and building spaces and opportunities for both formal and informal exchange between departments.

1. Introduction

SSH CENTRE (Social Sciences and Humanities for Climate, Energy aNd Transport Research Excellence) is a project funded by the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). The project aims to support cross-sectoral collaboration and empower citizens and networks to develop socially innovative solutions for the EU's climate transition, as well as strengthening SSH-STEM collaboration, transdisciplinary policy advice, inclusive engagement and SSH (Social Sciences and Humanities) communities across Europe. More information on the project is available via its website¹. In 2023, the project launched its Knowledge Brokerage (KB) Programme on Sustainability Transitions which aims to design and implement KB activities for climate, energy and mobility policy-making. The Programme involves 30 early- and mid-career researchers with an SSH background, organised into six teams, each of which is developing an SSH KB initiative in cooperation with a European city administration.

This is the follow-up report of the Knowledge Brokerage initiative “Transversality for circularity and sufficiency in Grenoble”. The initiative is developed in partnership with the City of Grenoble, Open City Office, represented by Nathalie Moyon & Xavier Perrin. The research team consists of Valentin Aubois-Liogier, Danijel Baturina, Laura Niessen and Timothy Peter Marcroft. The research team is supported by Daniele Mezzana and Luciano d’Andrea, on behalf of Knowledge & Innovation, which is an SSH CENTRE consortium partner, and by Marta Arosio (Energy Cities). The main objective of the KB initiative is to support knowledge exchange on promoting citizen sufficiency and circularity behaviours both within the municipality and from the municipality to the citizens of Grenoble².

2. Context and approach

2.1. The context in Grenoble

Grenoble is a city with a population of approximately 158,000 residents located in southeastern France. Set at the foot of the French Alps, it feels the effects of climate change more rapidly than elsewhere due to its location and the bowl-shaped topography of the valley. The city has been a frontrunner in sustainability and climate change action and was chosen as the European Green Capital in 2022.

The City of Grenoble shares local governance with other public actors. Some of the city’s *compétences* (domains of responsibility and power to act) are managed by the Grenoble-Alpes Métropole, a metropolitan government that combines 49 municipalities. The Métropole is responsible for social, cultural and economic development and housing, among other things. Grenoble is also part of a number of intermunicipal *syndicats* and mixed economy companies that manage services like public transit. The City of Grenoble retains responsibility for culture, some levels of primary education, sports, promotion of local democracy, relationships with associations, some aspects of urban planning, public health and environmental quality.

The Grenoble KB initiative focused on **resource sufficiency**³ and **circularity**. The City of Grenoble is involved in networks for circularity and sufficiency, developing action plans and strategies. A

1 SSH CENTRE website: <https://sshcentre.eu/>

2 Initially, it focused on resource efficiency, sufficiency and circularity. However, these concepts are interrelated and sufficiency encompasses both behavioural change and increased efficiency, so emphasis was placed on resource sufficiency and circularity.

3 In French: Sobriété

circular economy minimises waste and promotes reuse, while resource sufficiency challenges the prevailing norms of overconsumption, fostering a more sustainable relationship with resources. Sufficiency (*i.e.*, reduced unnecessary consumption of energy, materials, *etc.* without diminished quality of life) is a core principle for both the City of Grenoble and the Grenoble-Alpes metropolitan government. It has gained greater salience in the context of the energy crisis in 2022, when the French government advocated for energy sufficiency. Sufficiency can be applied beyond energy, advocating lower consumption of all resources (*e.g.*, material or transport sufficiency). The City of Grenoble supports sufficiency through its policies. So far, it has focused on its own competencies in promoting sufficiency, mainly raising awareness of energy sufficiency across its departments and users of municipality buildings and in public lighting. Grenoble has also made circularity a central tenet of its policies. The city is piloting circular economy initiatives across various departments and has a “Master Plan 2020-2030 for repair and reuse”. To implement circular measures, it collaborates with the Métropole, whose competencies include water, waste and public transport, as well as circular economy. The Métropole has created a Circular Economy Strategy for enterprises and a dedicated circularity space called “Pôle’R”.

2.2. Identified challenges

The team identified **two interrelated challenges**. The first is **influencing citizens’ behaviour for sufficiency and circularity**. The city has struggled to promote behaviour change towards circular living and sufficiency to its citizens. Concerns about intruding into personal matters and uncertainty about how to best communicate sustainable living were the main obstacles. The second challenge is the presence of knowledge and implementation siloes in the municipality. Sustainability actions often struggle with split competencies and limited horizontal coordination, leading to extra work and reduced knowledge exchange. The city recognises the need for more **transversality** and has taken measures for improvement (such as merging departments or creating project-oriented teams). Siloed information can hamper effective communication with citizens. Each employee with citizen contact acquires information about practices, preferences, and beliefs. In addition, the interaction between the municipality and citizens creates new knowledge, *e.g.*, about intervention effectiveness. If this information remains “trapped” in the department or organisational strata that acquired it, other employees and departments lose out. This dynamic creates a need for knowledge brokerage, both within the administration and between the city and its inhabitants.

The team argues that the first need (behaviour change) is related to the second (transversality): **a transversal approach incorporating knowledge brokerage could help to support citizens’ engagement for sufficiency**. The lack of transversality leads to unawareness of specialised services and of the expertise and developments of others. Knowledge and information sharing can increase circularity, by facilitating access to information and providing incentives for circular economy information sharing⁴. Moreover, knowledge exchange in socio-professional networks (*i.e.* transversality between services) enables the adaptive management needed to overcome complex socio-ecological issues⁵. While the current specialisation of municipal services through technical expertise might be needed to address specific issues, an additional transversal approach could bring complementary benefits, creating better conditions for coordination across the organisation and putting into practice a multidimensional vision of sustainability⁶.

4 Moritz Jäger-Roschko and Moritz Petersen, « Advancing the circular economy through information sharing: A systematic literature review », *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 369, October 2022.

5 Roy Bouwer, Lorena Pasquini and Marie-Ange Baudoin, « Breaking down the silos: Building resilience through cohesive and collaborative social networks », *Environmental Development*, vol. 39, September 2021.

6 Maj-Britt Quitzau, Sara Gustafsson, Birgitte Hoffmann, *et al.*, « Sustainability coordination within forerunning Nordic municipalities – Exploring structural challenges across departmental silos and hierarchies », *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 335, February 2022.

2.3. Knowledge brokerage methods

To address the two identified challenges and support knowledge brokerage, the team used a municipality-internal survey and hosted two parallel workshops, both on transversality and behaviour change, the first with Grenoble city staff and the second with 6 other European municipalities.

First, as examining practitioners' competencies is key for collaboration in a knowledge brokerage initiative⁷, **a survey** was sent to different city departments to gather information on knowledge and practices related to citizen behaviour change towards sufficiency and circularity and their relevant transversality approaches. The survey was aimed at collecting information for the first parallel workshop and to inform recommendations. It was built and administered online by the research team and distributed to the various municipal departments by Nathalie Moyon on the city's intranet and by email. The survey collected information on knowledge, policies and experiences related to public engagement for behaviour change, as well as transversality between departments on this topic. The process of building the survey required a brief literature review to identify relevant topics and issues, and to build the team's background on the relationships between transversality and behaviour change toward circularity. All participants confirmed that they understood the conditions of data collection and processing.

The following definitions were given to the respondents:

- *Sufficiency*: Measures and changes to daily practices to reduce demands on energy and resources while both respecting planetary limits and maintaining human well-being.
- *Transversality*: Collaborating or exchanging information between different people working in different departments of an organisation (community, company, association, etc.). These different departments can sometimes be organised into technical or administrative silos.

In April, during the City Hub visit to Grenoble, **two parallel half-day workshops** were hosted by the team and additional discussions and workshops were put on by the SSH CENTRE partners.

Workshop 1 was internal, aimed at agents of the City of Grenoble. It was held in French and divided into three main sessions. The first session was a brief presentation on citizen behaviour change to focus on the importance of transversality within this topic and to structure the discussion. The second session involved the participants teaching one another and learning collectively in a World Café format (*i.e.*, groups rotate between tables with different questions on different dimensions of the topic). Finally, the third session had the participants discussing the shared values of the municipality and ideas for transversality.

Workshop 2 was held in English and involved six representatives from other municipalities across Europe: Amsterdam (NL), Guimaraes (PT), Cork (IR), Forest (BE), Brussels (BE), and Turin (IT). The representatives reflected on their experience with regard to transversality and sustainability behaviour change. A follow-up world cafe session allowed for discussion to identify learnings for Grenoble based on the representatives' experience.

In addition, the team benefited from participating in other City Hub organised workshops on the themes of knowledge brokerage and sustainability that were held during the event, and these experiences contribute to the insights and observations shared in this report

⁷ Helka Kalliomäki, Sampo Ruoppila and Jenni Airaksinen, « It takes two to tango: Examining productive interactions in urban research collaboration », Research Evaluation, October 2021.

3. Insights from the survey and the workshops

3.1. Survey analysis

The participants (21) were **mainly managers or senior managers**, often with **multidisciplinary training** – which already represents a certain transversality – at the Masters level or above, supplemented by various professional experiences. Some also indicated that they rely on **activist experiences** or **personal interests towards ecology**. Nearly half have positions directly **related to the ecological transition**.

Part 1: On sufficiency

Professional experiences with sufficiency

A **large majority have at least one professional experience related to sufficiency**: hosting workshops, organising events, studies, project management, awareness work, or training on the subject. One third say they integrate sufficiency into their work or have sufficiency-related responsibilities. They report different experiences of raising awareness among the population (8) and raising awareness among colleagues (4) – some (2) have participated in workshops and training on sufficiency. Others (4), however, do not have professional experience relating to sufficiency, because their responsibilities are too far removed from this subject.

How sustainability issues impact your work

Sustainability issues today seem to be **truly integrated into the work of city employees**, whether through professional responsibilities, changes in everyday actions (at work and at home), proximity to the workplace or remote work, through sharing experiences, or even in the alignment between one's personal ecological convictions and one's work. For some, these issues have impacted their work since the start of their careers and others (2) specify that their positions exist thanks to the increasing importance of sustainability and sufficiency. Overall, some report increased consideration of sufficiency in their work (9).

Several practices are already in place for greater sufficiency, such as changing clothes to adapt to lower heating or working from home. Concrete discussions to develop energy and resource sufficiency in the city are taking place. These involve a change in professional practices in upkeep and maintenance, for example for municipal gardeners.

Contacts with residents on subjects tied to sufficiency

Nearly half of the people said they had **little or no contact with the residents of Grenoble**. Being that respondents were mainly managers or senior managers, we observe that these contacts are not very present at the management level. However, the other half of respondents are in **contact with residents generally as a part of their professional responsibilities** (e.g., school cafeterias, public lighting, etc.) **or specifically during workshops organised for that purpose**.

Encouragement towards greater sufficiency among residents

The answers on encouraging more sufficiency in the behaviour of residents follow the same patterns as those in contact with the population. Different means of encouraging change are

mentioned: publishing reports, organising workshops, education & awareness, action plans, or reflections carried out to understand the perspectives of users or city employees. The **role of building users** is often highlighted.

Part 2: On Transversality

Professional experiences with transversality

The answers given show that **the professional responsibilities of municipal employees require knowledge exchanges, internally, externally, or both**. Every respondent gave one or more examples of work carried out between different departments. Internally, transversality is often around a **common project** (e.g., project management, writing a report) or a **daily practice** of exchanging knowledge between departments. Externally, examples of transversality involved **associations or institutional partners**, local or otherwise, **local businesses**, or the **population**.

The double dimension of transversality – exchange of existing knowledge and creation of new knowledge – is found in the responses.

There is a **consensus** – discussed later – **on the fact that knowledge sharing exists within the municipality**.

Knowledge exchanges are mainly internal: around **municipal projects** (e.g., reports, maps, project monitoring), through **transversal projects** (e.g., Shared Data Observatory, “I invite you to my department” event), or specifically with the aim of **sharing information** (e.g., study results, news, financing opportunities, calls for projects).

Information sharing is also done externally, with **local, national, and international partners:** setting up and monitoring European projects (including the Knowledge Brokerage Programme of the SSH CENTRE), partnerships with associations and companies, or sharing experiences with other cities (e.g., Sfax in Tunisia).

Figures 1 - 4: Frequency of internal knowledge-sharing and collaborative practices & General assessment of transversality

2. In the last 12 months of your work, how often have you exchanged information with another municipal department?

3. On a scale from 1 to 5: how well do you think that Grenoble’s municipal administration functions in terms of knowledge sharing between departments?

4. On a scale from 1 to 5: how well do you think that Grenoble’s municipal administration functions in terms of knowledge sharing between the city and its inhabitants?

What works well in terms of transversality

Several elements are highlighted as working well regarding transversality between municipal departments and exchanges between the municipality and residents.

Between departments, information is shared through events such as **work meetings or training**, by such as the **Galaxy intranet platform**, or **memos** sent to the correct addressees. We note, however, that 5 people chose here to mention things that do not work well (e.g., divided departments, lack of clarity in the org chart, etc.). “Parallel networks” (whose precise definition is unclear) and “informal discussions”, “goodwill” or even “word of mouth” are also mentioned as a means of effective knowledge sharing.

Between the municipality and residents, **printed communication media** are highlighted (e.g., posters, a municipal magazine, notice boards), as well as **digital media** (e.g., newsletters, City

website), and **institutional structures which make it possible to have an easily identified contact person** (e.g., residents' centre, associations' centre, reception at the city hall).

What could be improved in terms of transversality

As shown by the responses summarised in Figure 3, and despite transversality observed in previous answers, the respondents think that **knowledge sharing between departments is not satisfactory**. This can be explained by a desire **to improve the existing transversality**. Considering the areas for improvement proposed below, it seems that specific inter-departmental projects that are indeed transversal are contrasted with a **lack of transversality at the senior management level and the city's major strategic orientations**.

Several avenues are proposed to improve this knowledge sharing between departments: **more collaboration with the communication department** when publishing information, **planned inter-department discussions around important themes** (e.g., the City budget), an easily accessible **newsletter on city projects**, streamlining internal visa deadlines and signature of letters, **promoting the advantages of sharing knowledge between departments**, giving employees **the time they need to collaborate** by relieving them of certain tasks, **changing departmental structure** to align with the needs and missions of the city, and trying to **overcome political and administrative divisions** that can harm transversal efforts. It seems that the departments are "very compartmentalised in their operation" and information sharing. Information coming down from the management to the employees is "not always clear or even transmitted". It is difficult for employees to know "**who does what**" and **this can result in the feeling of "wandering"** between departments without finding answers. The responses evoke a **need for clarity and a shared overview of municipal, administrative, and political actions & strategies**.

Concerning transversality between the city and residents: **better communication on projects** in the public interest proposed and put in place by the City, better **integration of the requests and comments** of residents, **presentation of public policies** (for example during an annual event where city employees and residents meet and learn about one another), and **strengthening transparency** in decision-making around major orientations.

Finally, respondents note that digital platforms (Galaxy or the City's website) would benefit from an update to improve information sharing.

Where do city employees turn for information

In practice, for the people who responded, the search for information from another department mainly goes through **a known contact who will be used to redirect them to the right person, with the head of the department** as an intermediary person, a **person from the department**, or the **person responsible for the subject directly** if they know them. Referral to the person holding the information can also be done by **reception at the City Hall**, by calling the **secretary or executive assistant of the department** concerned, by the **internal directory**, and by the **intranet** (or even the **internet**).

3.2. Insights from Workshop 1

In groups at four tables, Workshop 1 participants discussed the subject corresponding to that table with the help of questions and a discussion framework. The groups rotated after a set duration, encountering each of the topics, giving them the opportunity to gradually create a common understanding.

Table 1 – Tables and topics in Workshop 1

Tables	Topics
Table 1	External values & norms. The meeting of different values & social norms impacting the transition among the population of Grenoble.
Table 2	Exemplarity. Exemplary administration? The municipality of Grenoble as an example for its residents in terms of energy and resource sufficiency.
Table 3	Democracy. Involving residents & users (consultation, participation, citizen initiatives, etc.) in the creation of new social norms towards greater sufficiency.
Table 4	Internal values & norms. The role of values shared by municipal employees around sufficiency and the involvement of residents.

External values & norms

The mobilisation of values and social norms in the change towards more sufficiency directly calls into question **the municipality's perception of the city's residents: how to take into account the real differences while remaining inclusive and avoiding judgements via stereotypes?** The promotion of new values and social norms linked to practices of sufficiency is already underway in the municipality and could be developed further. In doing so, **the City could become a model of important changes for residents.**

Exemplarity

The City's role as a laboratory of sufficient practices, to serve as an example to the population, is well understood by the workshop participants. They even suggest going **beyond exemplarity.** However, there are internal obstacles to this dynamic, with possible **political dissensions in governance**, and externally as well, with the **population's possible lack of trust or defiant posture** towards the municipality. Communication and roles dedicated to sufficiency could be strengthened.

Democracy

The city has a **wide range of democratic practices and tools**, ranging from simple consultation to deliberative bodies, without forgetting concrete examples of co-creation of the city, such as composting or gardening in public space. The advantages of a rich and varied democratic life are highlighted, in particular the virtuous cycle that can be built between **participation, empowerment, concrete practices, improved living environment, the desirability of sufficient behaviour and the acceptability of public policies** in this direction. The difficulty of implementing such experiments **without drifting into interference in personal decisions** and **without a firm grasp of future norms** that will be created there should not, however, be neglected

Internal values & norms

The participants, and certainly a good portion of the city's agents and elected officials, share **values related to sufficiency**: responsibility towards future generations, the importance of quality of life in Grenoble, the urgency to act, and, in particular, **social cohesion**. The city employees adopt a set of concrete practices to embody their values around sufficiency in their work. That being said, divergences in values and norms create **dissonance in the actions** undertaken by the city and make them less effective and less well accepted by the population, which highlights the **need for mediation** and the **search for sources of cohesion** within municipal teams. The municipality, like the population, is made up of various groups which show **differences (even inequalities)** in their relationships to energy, transport, and comfort, requiring flexibility in policy measures put in place and even in the definition of social cohesion.

3.3. Insights from Workshop 2

Workshop 2 was organised to allow knowledge exchange with external partners from other European municipalities. The workshop participants gathered in a World Café setting (similar to Workshop 1 above) to discuss insights. The discussion led to insights on both citizen engagement for behaviour change and transversality.

Transversality in the municipality

Transversality often occurs naturally due to the complexity of ecological problems, inviting various perspectives from different departments and stakeholders. **The Doughnut Economy**⁸ offers a holistic framework to address these issues. Successful transversality requires the right conditions and people, with leadership playing a crucial role. **Proactive leadership** should promote inter-departmental collaboration and recruit staff open to diverse perspectives.

Improving communication and personal relations between departments is also vital. Spotlighting good work through internal communications, like a “(Green) Employee of the Week” in newsletters, can motivate staff. Facilitating interpersonal relations, such as through networking events, helps build cross-departmental teams. Amsterdam's weekly sustainability events for staff are an example, emphasising the need for well-planned events that encourage mingling outside of employees' usual circles.

Barriers to transversality include **long communication chains and resistance to changing established working methods**. Training operational staff in sustainable practices can be challenging, as seen with gardeners resistant to environmentally-friendly methods. Solutions include **liaison officers to transmit knowledge** between departments and “breakthrough” experts to remove bureaucratic bottlenecks.

Engaging citizens

Effective communication with citizens is essential for promoting sufficiency and circularity. This requires **positive examples, clear benefits for stakeholders, and engaging, understandable language**. Communication strategies should evolve with the times, leveraging professional social media outputs and existing social relations. Engaging children can foster an ecological conscience and involve parents, while peer-to-peer approaches and spotlighting pioneers can inspire behavioural change. Projects should be presented as **joint efforts between the municipality and citizens to create legitimacy and interest**.

⁸ Florian Ross, « Kate Raworth - Doughnut Economics: Seven Ways to Think Like a 21st Century Economist (2017) », Regional and Business Studies, vol. 11, n° 2, December 2019.

Citizen participation and empowerment are crucial. **Citizens need space to propose solutions** on sufficiency and circular economy topics. **Direct engagement** with “average” citizens remains a challenge, necessitating more direct contact points and transparency about their role – whether they are being informed, consulted, or empowered. Tools such as citizen assemblies and new municipal jobs focused on community needs assessment were suggested to facilitate this process.

Table 2 – Transversality vs. Citizen Engagement in the Workshop 2 insights

Aspect	Transversality	Citizen Engagement
Focus	Collaboration within the municipality	Collaboration between citizens and the municipality
Challenges	Departmental silos, communication barriers	Reaching diverse populations, managing expectations
Solutions	Supportive leadership, improved communication, liaison officers	Positive communication, social media, citizen assemblies

3.4. Additional relevant insights

3.4.1. Fishbowl workshop

Aside from these workshops, the visiting cities and representatives from Grenoble also participated in a discussion in which a shifting set of speakers seated inside of a circle responded to questions from the audience in a dynamic and participatory fishbowl format.

Key insights:

- **Doughnut Economy Framework:** Several cities are adopting the doughnut economy framework⁹ to create positive narratives related to ecological challenges. The aim is to make this perspective relatable to citizens and their daily actions.
- **Radical Changes:** Radical changes are necessary to address significant challenges, but it is crucial to involve citizens. Questions arise on how to reach citizens, justify choices, develop a positive vision for the future, and shift local cultures (*e.g.*, reducing car dependency).
- **Participatory Budgeting:** This tool can foster engagement and promote social justice but faces challenges in implementation, especially in involving marginalised communities. Grenoble has struggled with broad, diverse engagement and is experimenting with targeted budgeting and “open build sites” to improve participation.
- **Role of Front-line Workers:** Front-line workers, such as social workers and gardeners, play a vital role in communicating with citizens about sufficiency and the circular economy. They need upskilling to effectively drive sustainable behaviour changes.

⁹ Florian Ross, « Kate Raworth - Doughnut Economics: Seven Ways to Think Like a 21st Century Economist (2017) », *Regional and Business Studies*, vol. 11, n° 2, December 2019.

- **HR Implications:** Transitioning to sustainable practices requires changes in working methods and management. Some employees may need to change jobs, necessitating careful consideration of their wellbeing.
- **Alternative Channels:** Raising environmental awareness can be achieved through schools and by linking topics like mobility changes with health impacts, such as children's health and air pollution.
- **Effective Tools:** Tools like the Climate Fresco (Fresque du Climat) can be effective for reaching staff and citizens but must be well-designed with clear objectives. Grenoble's experience highlights the potential for unintended consequences, such as creating conflict.

3.4.2. Best practice examples & key insights from the cities

Before Workshop 2, six partner cities joined the workshop to share their experiences and insights in citizen behaviour change for sufficiency and circularity.

City / Area	Key takeaways
Amsterdam	Exploring free spaces (e.g., squatted buildings) for sustainability initiatives (as laboratories of exploration for new solutions) and citizen engagement. Training "breakthrough workers" to break down bureaucratic bottlenecks for sustainability projects (working across the municipality, intervening where needed.)
Brussels	"Inspirons le quartier" project: citizen involvement in neighbourhood resilience initiatives (structured participation and ownership are essential). Shifting Economy strategy: mixed approach using incentives and regulations to encourage businesses towards sustainability (challenges of involvement and communication with stakeholders).
Cork	Success of a temporary public Energy Office offering information and assistance, highlighting the value of direct citizen contact points (direct contact with over 7,000 citizens) but they highlight issues of financial sustainability of such initiatives.
Forest	Végétalab program: citizen engagement through free native plant nursery in public spaces – fostering shared responsibility and long-term commitment. Importance of clear communication for successful cross-departmental collaboration.
Guimaraes	Phasing in a circularity strategy with positive incentives for waste reduction (e.g., tax breaks, recycled materials for community benefit) – behaviour change can be more agreeable for citizens if coupled with clear benefits.
Turin	TIPS4PED project: Citizen engagement through gamification and living labs as part of a clean energy district project. Importance of managing expectations along the spectrum of citizen engagement (inform, collaborate, empower) and key role of political support for new initiatives.

4. Recommendations for Grenoble

4.1. General recommendations distilled from the project

First, the KB team gives general recommendations on putting into place transversality, especially for sufficiency, and engaging citizens. Second, some specific avenues for reflection adapted to Grenoble with relevant tools are presented, before diving deeper in a third phase on three of these avenues and tools.

4.1.1. Transversality in the municipality

To make it easier for people to work together, it is important to **create ownership** of projects among the different departments.

It is important to **build strong interpersonal relations** between departments and provide opportunities for exchange.

The approach of **cross-departmental action researchers** that force breakthroughs might help Grenoble (who already has strong relationships with local researchers).

4.1.2. Engaging citizens

Show the **clear benefits of sustainability actions**, for instance through giving citizens something in exchange (*e.g.*, plants, materials for energy saving) or through benefiting parts of the community and communicating on this.

Citizens can be more involved and especially if their experiences are considered as valuable information. This could be done, for instance, through a living lab approach that can engage and empower citizens.

For communicating with citizens, it is important to **be transparent and manage expectations** of the extent to which they can become involved and the **nature and timing of later follow-up actions**.

Peer-to-peer approaches can be useful for information dissemination and behaviour change.

4.2. Some specific avenues for reflection and tools

Recommendation	Putting this in place in Grenoble	Relevant tools
TRANSVERSALITY		
1. Creating opportunities for informal exchange	Bring together staff members working in different city sites	Weekly (sustainability) networking event (Amsterdam example)
2. Actively addressing bottlenecks (i.e. administrative barriers that hinder change)	Train a team of cross-departmental workers	Breakthrough workers (Amsterdam example)
3. Working groups across departments	Teams of cross-departmental workers with connections to diverse parts of the municipality	Liaison workers (Forest example) "Cultural brokers" within the municipality that can act to bridge and bond the departments ¹⁰
4. Sharing information on ongoing work beyond departments	Intranet dashboard with feed populated by other departments	Newsletter with updates on sustainability work send to all departments; One suggestion was to add a "Green Employee of the Week" to highlight work done
5. National and international networks can play an important role in knowledge diffusion and best practices	Creating enabling conditions that would allow employees to join different initiatives related to sufficiency and circularity	List of relevant national and international networks Internal "networks calendar" – with relevant events and information
6. Empowered, knowledgeable, and mobilised frontline employees	Taking the new gardening practices as an example, ensure that employees with direct contact with the public understand the connections between their work and larger sustainability goals	Grenoble's own changes in their gardening practices
7. A focus on transversality during major strategic orientations	During city budget construction and other important moments, invite employee participation in a way that crosses departmental boundaries	Grenoble's own budget presentation events during the first term of the current administration
BEHAVIOUR CHANGE		
8. Creating clear benefits for citizens through sustainability projects	Doughnut workshops, school courtyard greening, and other citizen-directed projects are an opportunity for two-way communication	Giving items to citizens to participate (e.g., plants, energy-saving equipment); Clear communication (e.g., social media)
9. Increasing ownership of projects	Providing (continued) opportunities to involve citizens in projects; publicly highlighting their involvement	Communications around citizens' involvement (e.g., "Green citizen of the month"), exhibition on projects that came about through collaboration with public (Amsterdam example)

¹⁰ Amy C. Edmondson, Sujin Jang and Tiziana Casciaro, « Cross-Silo Leadership », Harvard Business Review, section Cross-functional management, May 2019.

10. Providing one clear contact point for citizens	Creating a go-to information desk for sustainability-related questions (e.g., on subsidies, projects in the neighbourhood)	One-stop-shop style offices: Sustainability citizen office (example of Cork Energy Office)
11. Giving citizens more information available in forms that are “ready to use”	Present data on sufficiency and circularity in a clear and attractive way Invite to action by using choice architecture principles, i.e. nudging ¹¹	Transparent and clear data on the websites to inform the citizens – style of information presented is important for citizens making choices ¹²
12. Activate key actors in the community to reach out (e.g., local firms or community leaders)	Grenoble’s robust research community and active civil society	Working through business associations (Brussels example)

4.3. A deeper dive on three of the above avenues and tools

In this section, we will provide more details on three of the above ideas for promoting sufficiency through transversality and citizen engagement: the role of frontline employees, the role of key citizen actors, and the opportunities of internal formal and informal exchanges.

Furthermore, and relevant to all three ideas below, the KB team argues for the need for **transdepartmental teams of workers with broad connections inside of the municipality**. These teams could be set up based on the workers across different departments already working on sustainability issues or people willing to do so (for example frontline employees; see section below). Indeed, the results of the survey show that a large number of management-level employees have already integrated sustainability issues into their daily work, and this could provide the starting point of working groups if they were able to identify each other. These working groups would be issue-focused and city-scale, meaning that each would have a specific set of related problems and opportunities to work on across all aspects of Grenoble’s operations and projects. They would serve to share information, develop proposals, and coordinate actions across departments.

4.3.1. Empowered, knowledgeable, and mobilised frontline employees

The KB team highlights the importance of municipal employees in contact with the population in the course of their duties (frontline employees): gardeners, workers in municipally run schools, project managers, librarians, social workers, or police, for example. As **contact points between the city and its inhabitants**, they play a decisive role in **translating political ambitions into policy into practice**, building organic relationships with citizens¹³, and **gathering the information** necessary to make good policy¹⁴.

Consulting with departmental administrators can help build an initial list of employees in regular contact with the public, likely spread across many departments. Among each set of frontline employees, some will be more open and sensitive to issues of sufficiency, or the ecological transition more broadly, than their colleagues. **Identifying these people** can be a useful early step, as they will likely be more motivated to participate in meetings and share information with the other members

11 Richard V. Adkisson, « Nudge: Improving Decisions About Health, Wealth and Happiness », *The Social Science Journal*, vol. 45, n° 4, December 2008.

12 *Ibid.*

13 Imrat Verhoeven and Evelien Tonkens, « Enabling civic initiatives: frontline workers as democratic professionals in Amsterdam », *Local Government Studies*, vol. 49, n° 4, July 2023.

14 Wieke Blijleven and Merlijn Van Hulst, « How Do Frontline Civil Servants Engage the Public? Practices, Embedded Agency, and Bricolage », *The American Review of Public Administration*, vol. 51, n° 4, May 2021.

of their teams. Alongside regularly disseminated opportunities to engage, a simple non-obligatory survey targeted specifically at frontline employees might be an easy way to identify these early adopters, as they will generally be more likely to respond (as our internal survey seemed to indicate). These representatives of teams of frontline employees could be integrated into a **transdepartmental working group**.

While environmental values are not something that managers can dictate, raising awareness about the impacts of climate change and resource depletion, in particular on working life, can help in becoming **effective ambassadors for the city's ambitions**. Frontline employees should have a positive vision of how their jobs contribute to the changes that the municipality is promoting, and be encouraged to put pro-environmental values they may hold into practice, as this can be **key to the success of new ecological initiatives**¹⁵. A positive example of this is Grenoble's change to their municipal gardening service, moving from a semi-industrial approach to one that casts the gardeners in the roles of guardians of the commons and sources of information for the public. Also, **for awareness-raising, not every tool is right for every job**. Grenoble has had mixed experiences with deploying the Climate Fresco¹⁶ among frontline employees, for example. When deciding on a tool for encouraging learning and discussion, representatives of the group meant to participate should be consulted and asked for feedback.

But knowledge generated in direct contact with citizens has to rise up the organisation chart as well. As the **main points of interaction between the municipality and citizens**, frontline employees are also **reservoirs of information** about the population that would otherwise be challenging to gather¹⁷. These employees often have interactions with different citizens or in contexts other than during formal participatory processes, which can often attract the "usual suspects". Capturing this information during the initial phases of planning and priority setting can be complementary to citizen consultation and participatory methods. Furthermore, frontline employees often have a general sense of how the populations they interact with feel about different policy interventions, which can serve as a valuable monitoring tool. While this frontline knowledge can be difficult to capitalise, doing so can help the city to achieve its goals¹⁸.

4.3.2. The role of key actors in the community

As presented in the Workshop 1, **shared values and norms** (e.g., social norms) are a **lever to change behaviours** towards sufficiency. For example, peer approval is a strong motivation for many, while not meeting expectations of peer groups can lead to disapproval and marginalisation¹⁹. Key local actors such as local community leaders or local businesses could help to **set and foster these new values and norms** by finding and promoting role models for the community. On a national scale, French people seem keen to change their behaviours, partly due to municipal efforts (for example in Grenoble), but many consider that they are already doing enough compared to others²⁰. It shows the need to collectively engage in change for sufficiency and thus the need to address these issues on a **societal level**, as well as an individual one. The municipality could aim to **connect with existing actors** to mutually reinforce sufficiency norms and behaviour alongside citizens and organisations. Key local actors could also help to remove political barriers thanks to their proximity with inhabitants and citizens²¹.

This process of engaging local key actors can only happen in a context of successful **cross-departmental collaboration**, with clear communication, as the city of Forest (Belgium) showed, and through devoting sufficient **time to discussions with local actors**. It is furthermore important to

15 Alexander Yuriev, Olivier Boiral and David Talbot, « Is there a place for employee-driven pro-environmental innovations? The case of public organizations », *Public Management Review*, vol. 24, n° 9, September 2022.

16 Climate Fresco website: <https://fresqueduclimat.org/>

17 Jun Ye, Detelina Marinova and Jagdip Singh, « Bottom-up learning in marketing frontlines: conceptualization, processes, and consequences », *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, vol. 40, no 6, November 2012.

18 *Ibid.*

19 Maria Sandberg, « Sufficiency transitions: A review of consumption changes for environmental sustainability », *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 293, April 2021.

20 ADEME, Baromètre Sobriétés et Modes de vie. Pratiques, représentations et aspirations des Français en matière de sobriété, Report, March 2024.

21 Gintare Stankuniene, Dalia Streimikiene and Grigorios L. Kyriakopoulos, « Systematic Literature Review on Behavioral Barriers of Climate Change Mitigation in Households », *Sustainability*, vol. 12, n° 18, September 2020.

engage the right contacts. The workshop representative from Brussels Environment mentioned that trying to connect to the community through local business associations was not always successful, since the associations did not see themselves as mediators for sustainability knowledge. To address citizens, **key sustainability figures might be identified.** This could be done through a competition or nomination for “green citizens” or “sufficiency champions”. Similar to the example provided by Amsterdam, these citizens could be celebrated (*e.g.*, in an exhibition) and their behaviour shared widely.

Moreover, to motivate behaviour, norms should become salient, while recognising that their degree of influence will change with times and contexts²². Therefore, from a bottom-up perspective and in order to understand these times and contexts as well as their evolution, key local actors should be involved at all times. Since frequency of action is central to setting norms, *i.e.* the occurrence of one behaviour, it is important to sustain behaviours towards sufficiency with these actors – and acceptable behaviours & unacceptable ones should be clearly defined²³.

The municipality could also work with existing organisations to promote sufficiency to their members or employees. The example of Pôle'R space with diverse businesses focused on sustainability and sufficiency shows that the municipality of Grenoble as well as Grenoble-Alpes Métropole are working in that direction. The businesses can continue to promote these values to their customers and staff through communication and diverse strategies²⁴ (*e.g.*, leaflets or workshops). Alongside social organisations, they could **ensure that sufficiency norms reach diverse parts of the Grenoble population** and help with **receiving feedback from citizens** about feasibility in their daily life.

4.3.3. Opportunities of internal formal & informal exchanges

The KB team emphasises the importance of **creating opportunities** for internal formal and informal information exchanges²⁵. While Grenoble demonstrates a commendable level of engagement with sufficiency issues, and our survey showed that many Grenoble employees have already integrated these issues into their daily work, there is potential to enhance knowledge exchange and collaboration, both internally and externally. This would strengthen the collaboration between Grenoble's stakeholders with a vested interest in enhancing sufficiency and could potentially be a building block of new, more effective internal networks²⁶.

Our analysis highlights the need to bridge some gaps between formal and informal knowledge exchange. While formal channels such as intranet platforms and departmental meetings exist, they often fall short of fostering a truly collaborative environment, according to the survey results. Informal networks, based on personal relationships and shared interests, appear to be effective in facilitating knowledge sharing and solution-finding. To enhance their impact, they should be open and strong. The goal is to **foster the flow of information in all directions** within city administration: from bottom to top, from top to bottom and horizontally across departments.

To optimise knowledge exchange and transversality, Grenoble could benefit from a hybrid approach that **combines the strengths of both formal and informal channels.** This might involve creating dedicated spaces for professionally relevant but still informal interaction within the city administration, such as knowledge cafés or innovation and information hubs (especially for bringing together staff members working in different sites). Also, those efforts can be connected to opportunities for informal discussion and inputs on key aspects of the city's work. Bringing elected officials, city employees, and citizens together to discuss the yearly budget, as was done in the first term of Grenoble's current administration, can serve as an example, especially if this were structured to include more horizontal communication between attendees.

²² Adrienne Chung and Rajiv N. Rimal, « Social norms: A review », *Review of Communication Research*, vol. 4, 2016.

²³ *Ibid.*

²⁴ N.M.P. Bocken and S.W. Short, « Towards a sufficiency-driven business model: Experiences and opportunities », *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, vol. 18, March 2016.

²⁵ Tung-Mou Yang and Terrence A. Maxwell, « Information-sharing in public organizations: A literature review of interpersonal, intra-organizational and inter-organizational success factors », *Government Information Quarterly*, vol. 28, n° 2, April 2011.

²⁶ Keith G. Provan and H. Brinton Milward, « Do Networks Really Work? A Framework for Evaluating Public-Sector Organizational Networks », *Public Administration Review*, vol. 61, n° 4, [American Society for Public Administration, Wiley], 2001.

Additionally, recognizing and supporting certain **liaison workers** (as in the Forest example) or **cultural brokers** (recognized as important for connecting and engaging experts inside and outside of the organisations) can help **bridge departments and create opportunities** for information exchanges. Other aspects could be to develop a formal and informal mentorship program within city administration which would pair employees with ones from different departments to transfer knowledge and skills, **fostering a culture of learning, information sharing and collaboration**. That would promote the **creation of future breakthrough workers** within the city administration (similar to the Amsterdam example).

The effective flow of information within the city can boost positive signals and be a “fire starter” of new types of initiatives and foster transversality related to sufficiency. New types of formal and informal exchanges could be steps towards developing new forms of experimentation in the context of sustainability transitions²⁷ and add to Grenoble’s efforts towards its vision of a sustainable future.

27 James Evans, Andrew Karvonen and Rob Raven (dir.), *The Experimental City*, 1st ed., Abingdon, Oxon; New York, NY: Routledge, 2016.

5. Conclusion

This is the follow-up report for the Knowledge Brokerage (KB) initiative “Transversality for circularity and sufficiency in Grenoble” with the objectives to **support knowledge exchange, both within the municipality and from the municipality towards the citizens of the city, and to promote sufficient and circular behaviour**. The team identified two main challenges for the City of Grenoble. First, the city struggles to influence citizens’ behaviour for circularity and sufficiency. Second, and relatedly, a more transversal approach could help to support citizens’ engagement for sufficiency. To address these challenges, the team applied different methods of knowledge brokerage: first, a survey for staff members was circulated to understand the situation; then, one French-language workshop with municipal staff members and stakeholders was held, and, in parallel, one English-language workshop with representatives from other municipalities brought in external expertise. These different tools were used to understand how the City of Grenoble works in terms of transversality, where improvements could be made and how **these changes could help drive behaviour change towards sufficiency**.

The team developed general recommendations and twelve specific avenues for action based on the survey, the workshops, and academic literature on transversality and behaviour change. The recommendations address both how to improve transversality across the municipality and communication with its citizens, as well as how to encourage behaviour change among the populace. For transversality, general recommendations were to **create ownership of projects across departments, build strong interpersonal relationships and train a team of breakthrough workers**. For citizen engagement, it was recommended to **show the clear benefits of sustainability actions, involve citizens and use their knowledge, communicate transparently and use peer-to-peer approaches to disseminate norms**. For all twelve action avenues, relevant tools are provided that might be suitable to the Grenoble context. Three of the twelve avenues were considered particularly promising and explored in greater detail for the Grenoble context. The team recommends that **Grenoble uses its frontline workers** to facilitate contact with citizens about sufficiency topics. Frontline workers are direct representatives of the city and can therefore share its strategic focus with the public, while collecting feedback from citizens. Another recommendation is to **use key actors in the community to spread new values and norms**. The city could connect to local actors, both individuals and organisations (e.g., civil society groups, NGOs, businesses, universities) to normalise sufficiency behaviour and understand how the required transformation can be made socially feasible and just. The final recommendation focuses more on transversality within the municipality. The workshops identified **potential for the City of Grenoble to facilitate exchanges between staff members, both informally and formally**, to increase collaboration and knowledge exchange. One example could be a mentorship programme within the city administration.

We recognize that such changes to the practice and working routines of civil servants can be challenging to achieve in practice as **fostering collaboration across departments requires initiative and resources from management**. New, proactive styles of leadership are needed to encourage the inclusion of diverse stakeholders. Improved citizen engagement requires innovative tools and direct communication channels both vertically and horizontally. Time is key for implementation and outside perspectives can be helpful in these processes. We encourage Grenoble to continue its productive partnerships with local universities, as well as participation in research projects such as this one, which can help broker the **knowledge that is one essential step on the path toward a sustainable and thriving city**.

Finally, while this report focuses mainly on the role of humans and social structures, **sufficiency issues are present throughout the non-human environment** as well. Therefore, the team invites the municipality of Grenoble to carry out their work on sufficiency with this broader perspective in mind. The observation and analysis of social interactions should take into account everything that is part of them beyond humans. For example, during a meeting or public presentation, the build or natural environment, the room layout, the objects, the temperature and everything participating in the human exchanges can shape the way communication is both made and received, and thus the perceptions, beliefs, and behaviours of the people participating. This **expanded view of the non-human environment** could enhance the understanding of internal and external dynamics.

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